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Conditions and pathways for a climate club to reach a more ambitious global treaty

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Abstract

Despite the Paris Agreement, countries worldwide persist in non-harmonized and weak climate policies, triggered by concerns about competitiveness and trade effects. In view of this, the concept of a “climate club” of countries appears to be a promising complement to the Paris Agreement. This study sheds light on the potential of such a club through the use of an agent-based model that explores its dynamics and convergence to a stable coalition. The model describes 31 heterogeneous (blocks of) countries calibrated on empirical data concerning carbon emissions, abatement costs, domestic carbon prices, and the relative change in export volume upon the introduction of a border carbon tariff. In each period, non-members evaluate the possibility to join the club, while club members consider the option of leaving it, based on trading-off costs and benefits. The iterative process of joining and leaving is repeated until a stable coalition emerges in which no country wants to change its membership status. We run the model for 117 scenarios that capture a variation in the values of four key parameters: the initial coalition, the uniform carbon price of the club, the stringency of the border tariff, and the allocation of tariff revenues. An additional scenario is developed to capture the implications of WTO rules. The results indicate that achieving global coverage by a club created by the European Union alone or together with the United States has a high likelihood under a sufficiently stringent border tariff, equal to or higher than the club’s carbon price. Moreover, a partial return of the tariff revenues to non-members helping them cover abatement costs serves both to mitigate the risk of trade retaliation and to further motivate outsiders to join the club.

Keywords

Abatement, carbon price, harmonized policy, international trade, border carbon adjustment.

1 Introduction

Diplomatic efforts in the past 30 years to combat climate change have culminated in the 2015 Paris Agreement. Many celebrate it for being signed by nearly all countries (covering over 98% of global GHG emissions) and for aiming to limit global warming between 1.5°C and 2°C above pre-industrial levels. However, several doubts have been raised about its effectiveness (Falkner, 2016; van den Bergh et al., 2020; Nordhaus, 2021).

First, the Paris pledges do not guarantee consistent policies as there are no mechanisms to enforce committed emission reductions nor minimum reduction targets. Instead, the Paris agreement relies entirely on moral pressure from other members. In fact, since the climate is a global public good, it is often beneficial for countries not to pursue their reduction commitments. They can rely on mitigation efforts of other countries without contributing to costly abatement. This is known as free-riding (Buchanan, 1965; Nordhaus, 2015). Moreover, the diversity of nations' conditions and interests, including high- vs low-income and fossil-fuel importers vs exporters, translates into enormous differences in ambitions and policies. This, in turn, triggers carbon leakage which undercuts the effectiveness of the Paris Agreement (King and van den Bergh, 2021).

Because of these shortcomings, the combined Paris Agreement pledges of all members fall significantly short of keeping global warming beneath the 1.5 or even the 2°C thresholds (Fawcett et al., 2015, Iyer et al., 2022, Climate Action Tracker, 2023). Indeed, GHG emissions increased by 1.2% from 2021 to 2022, reaching a new all-time high (UNEP, 2023). According to the UNEP's Emissions Gap Report (2023), under current pledges for 2030, the world is heading for a 2.5-2.9°C temperature rise above pre-industrial levels.

In response, researchers have advocated an alternative climate strategy, namely the climate club. Originally proposed by Victor (2011), it represents a dynamic agreement that expands over time rather than immediately requiring participation of all countries. The club strategy recognises differences in motivation and resources among countries, allowing frontrunners to join the club and encourage others to do so in later stages.

Whereas the Paris Agreement has not overcome free-riding by countries, an expanding climate club can achieve this by harmonising policy in an initial club of ambitious member countries, and in subsequent stages encourage or even pressure others to join (Falkner et al., 2021). Several variations of the original climate club design have been proposed (Keohane et al., 2015; Hovi et al., 2017; van den Bergh, 2017; Sprinz et al., 2018; Martin and van den Bergh, 2019; Paroussos et al., 2019; Shaw and Fu, 2020; Gersbach et al., 2021; Hermwille et al., 2022). It has been argued that an expanding climate club could be complementary to, or even create positive synergy with, the current Paris Agreement (van den Bergh et al., 2020). The idea of a climate club has also been picked up outside the academic world (Tagliapietra, 2020; Shaia and Colgan, 2021; Tagliapietra and Wolff, 2021a; and Tagliapietra and Wolff, 2021b). However, still little is known about the potential dynamics of a climate club, notably under what conditions, through which pathways, and with what likelihood a club will develop into an ambitious climate agreement covering all nations. This will be the focus of our research.

2 Key considerations in modelling a climate club

2.1 Club topology

The idea of clubs in international relations is not new. They occur in the form of military alliances or international trade groups. An example of a successful international club is the WTO/GATT, founded in 1947 with 23 members and now comprising 164 countries (van den Bergh et al., 2020). The WTO has successfully reduced the average trade tariff between participants by 17% between 1947 and 1999 (Bown and Irwin, 2017). Even in climate policy, for many years clubs have existed in some form. However, not all clubs work the same way. Falkner et al. (2021) distinguish between three types of clubs: normative, bargaining and transformational. The goal of normative clubs is to bring together countries that share policy ambitions and convince other countries to adopt these ambitions. Bargaining clubs aim to form a unified front in multilateral negotiations, to increase their diplomatic position. Both normative and bargaining clubs are common in international relations. The climate clubs proposed by Victor (2011), Nordhaus (2015) and others are transformational

clubs. These clubs have binding emission reduction commitments, which are enforced through access to club goods for members and sanctions on non-members. The goal of transformational clubs is to grow and to transform the climate policies of as many countries as possible. This is in contrast with most normative and bargaining clubs, whose purpose is remaining stable. In reality transformational clubs for climate policy do not yet exist.

2.2 Properties of the climate club

Nordhaus (2015) lists four conditions for clubs to be successful:

1. access to club goods for members,
2. non-members can be sanctioned at relatively low cost,
3. the club is beneficial for all members,
4. the club is stable.

Access to club goods is the defining feature of the climate club. It is this incentive structure that overcomes free-riding and enforces the targets of the club. Researchers have proposed various climate clubs with different club goods. These club goods must have two basic properties for a club to be successful. First, the club good must be a public good which can be shared by the club members. Second, it must be possible to exclude non-members from accessing the club good at relatively low cost for club members.

Conditions 2, 3 and 4 all have to do with the stability of the club. Unstable clubs do not exist long and will not achieve their goal. For clubs to be stable, membership should be beneficial for all members. This means that the dues of the club should be less than (or at least equal to) the benefits from club goods access. This is only feasible if sanctioning non-members can be done at low costs for club members. If not, dues of the club will be high and benefits will likely not outweigh the costs. It is good to note that the term sanctioning is used here in a broad context. It can range from imposing trade tariffs on non-members to simply excluding non-members from the club good.

2.3 Club goods

The original club good proposed by Nordhaus (2015) is preferential market access for members. Nordhaus achieves this by imposing trade tariffs on all non-members, prohibiting them free access to markets of climate club members. Trade tariffs also generate revenue, which helps cutting the costs of excluding non-members due to lost trade revenue. However, there is some debate about the legality of such trade tariffs under WTO rules (van den Bergh et al., 2020; Falkner et al., 2021). A solution is to implement region-specific border carbon adjustments (BCA) instead of uniform tariffs (Paroussos et al., 2019; van den Bergh et al., 2020; Tagliapietra and Wolff, 2021a). While the WTO legality of BCA is still not undisputed, there are exceptions in WTO regulation which could permit BCA (Fischer and Fox, 2012).

Members of the WTO must respect the non-discrimination principles laid out in the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT). The Most-Favoured-Nation treatment (GATT Article I) bans discriminatory treatment between trade partners, including tariffs. Furthermore, the national treatment (GATT Article III) mandates members to ensure equal treatment of both imported and domestically produced goods. In principle, any internal tax or penalties not levied on domestic goods must not be imposed on foreign ones either (Lim et al., 2021, World Trade Organization, 2023a).

If climate club regions aim to respect WTO agreements while implementing a region-specific BCA that may deviate from the carbon price of the club, they will have to justify themselves based on the GATT Article XX concerning General Exceptions (Böhringer et al., 2022, World Trade Organization, 2023b). This article states that “WTO members may adopt policy measures that are inconsistent with GATT disciplines, but necessary to protect human, animal or plant life or health (paragraph (b)), or relating to the conservation of exhaustible natural resources (paragraph (g))” (World Trade Organization, 2023b). Settling the dispute on the WTO legality can be developed by moving forward with BCA and letting a WTO panel settle conflicts, establishing precedent

for future conflicts (Bhagwati and Mavroidis, 2007). Predictably, the feasibility of this strategy increases with the size of the climate club.

Moreover, an additional benefit of BCA is that they are better in reducing carbon leakage than uniform tariffs. However, Paroussos et al. (2019) find that BCA are worse at inducing new members into the climate club compared to uniform tariffs (Nordhaus, 2015). This is because uniform tariffs affect a larger share of global trade flow than BCA, since uniform tariffs affect both low and high carbon exports.

Some also worry that imposing tariffs may lead to trade conflicts, resulting in high costs for both members and non-members. BCA might be less likely to trigger trade conflicts than uniform tariffs, but there is little data on the matter. One solution is recycling (a part of) the revenue of uniform tariffs or BCA back to the country of origin - “revenue recycling offsets” - either temporarily or as permanent club design (van den Bergh, 2017, Shaw and Fu, 2020). Such recycling could prevent trade conflicts, while still addressing carbon leakage. However, it does decrease the value of the club good by limiting the sanctions on non-members. Revenue recycling can be returned unconditionally or specifically earmarked to support domestic industries in adopting low-carbon production technologies, thereby reducing the abatement costs associated with joining the club and implementing its carbon price (van den Bergh, 2017, van den Bergh et al., 2020). Making use of revenue recycling can be a useful tool to get the climate club to a critical mass, after which its economic power is enough to fend off trade retaliations.

2.4 Carbon leakage

Carbon leakage can seriously undermine global mitigation by stimulating emissions in countries with weaker climate policies (King and van den Bergh, 2021). Therefore, an additional success condition should be added for climate clubs: they address carbon leakage. The most straightforward way to do this is with BCA. In this case, countries implement good-specific tariffs based on their carbon footprint to account for the domestic carbon price. Estimating carbon footprints of goods is difficult, because production processes differ among countries. The most accurate estimate would be based on the carbon intensity of the foreign production process. However, in reality this carbon intensity can be very hard to estimate. Using carbon intensity of similar goods is a pragmatic solution, but potentially less accurate (Rocchi et al., 2018).

Nordhaus (2015) mentions the idea of a BCA, but it is not implemented in his model. He chooses to use uniform import tariffs instead, due to their simplicity and transparency. This is because he uses a top-down approach, where he tries to show what the final stage of a successful climate club looks like. Indeed, a climate club covering the whole world and with harmonized carbon prices does not have leakage. However, climate clubs which do not have harmonized carbon prices or cover only part of the globe suffer from carbon leakage (Fowle, 2009; Peters et al., 2011).

2.5 Climate damages

A difficult issue in climate modelling is incorporating climate damages. First, due to the complex nature of the climate there is considerable uncertainty about estimates of potential climate damage. There is debate about the underlying assumptions of the damage estimations, which have a significant impact on the outcome of these estimates (Howard and Sterner, 2017). Second, the global public good nature of the climate that gives rise to free-riding limits the impact of climate damage estimates on national climate policy decisions. Mitigation costs are borne nationally, whereas the benefits are enjoyed globally. This means that the avoided climate damages are usually too small to have an impact on the decision-making process of single countries. Only when global cooperation is enforced and free-riding is addressed do climate damage estimates start having an influence on national climate policy decisions. One example of this is a climate club that already covers a significant share of world emissions.

A popular way to express climate damages is the Social Cost of Carbon (SCC), which captures the marginal cost of emitting one additional unit of CO₂. It aims to capture all future costs resulting from CO₂ emissions, such as increased healthcare spending, loss of land to rising sea-levels or loss of farmland due to global warming. The SCC is generally estimated using integrated-assessment models (IAMs, see Hope, 2006). It was pioneered by Nordhaus (1991), who used it as a central

concept in his later DICE/RICE models. Debate about the estimates was ignited by Stern (2006), who obtained significantly higher estimates than his peers at the time, prompting several responses and alternative estimates (Hope, 2006; Tol and Yohe, 2007; Nordhaus, 2007). While the SCC provides a simple tool for policy makers to quantify the cost of climate damages, it has been criticized for its high level of uncertainty (Ackerman and Stanton, 2011; Pindyck, 2019). For example, Nordhaus (2019) finds estimates between 43 - 279 USD per ton CO₂ for 2020 in his DICE-2016 model, one of the most widely used IAMs. In the case of the recent Greenhouse Gas Impact Value Estimator (GIVE) model by Rennert et al. (2022), the estimates range between 44 - 413 2020-USD/tCO₂, with a mean SCC value of 185 USD/tCO₂. These ranges becomes much wider in other models. The reason for this uncertainty is the sensitivity of the SCC to the model parameters. This is especially true for the discount factor (Anthoff and Tol, 2011; Wang et al., 2019). A large part of climate damages are incurred in the future. To address this, future costs are weighted by a discount factor, which greatly affect the estimates. Finally, it is common practice for SCC estimates to represent various future scenarios with some probability distribution (van den Bergh and Botzen, 2014). It is argued by Weitzman (2009) that catastrophic scenarios should receive special attention. Doing so results in considerably higher estimates when using the DICE model (Botzen and van den Bergh, 2012).

2.6 Top-down versus bottom-up

Apparent failure of classic top-down negotiation strategies for combating climate change (Sabel and Victor, 2015) has prompted researchers to look for alternative approaches. Some have argued the use of bottom-up negotiation strategies (Weischer et al., 2012; Smead et al., 2014; Sabel and Victor, 2015; Keohane and Victor, 2016; Balint et al., 2017). These promote negotiations between small like-minded groups before negotiations with all parties begin. This reduces the complexity of the final negotiations by effectively reducing the number of demands to be aligned.

Climate clubs are generally considered a bottom-up strategy, as they start out with few members and gradually grow in size (Sabel and Victor, 2015; Keohane and Victor, 2016). However, most simulated climate club models actually use a top-down approach, including Nordhaus (2015). This is because they take the form of computable general equilibrium models (Nordhaus, 2015; Paroussos et al., 2019; Shaw and Fu, 2020). Such models deal well with static situations, telling us which types of climate clubs are feasible and stable at a given moment in time. However, they provide little insight into how stable solutions can be achieved along a dynamic path. The theoretical debate on the subject, where emphasis is put on the bottom-up nature of climate clubs, provides suggestions about how this dynamics may unfold (Smead et al., 2014; Sabel and Victor, 2015; Keohane and Victor, 2016; van den Bergh et al., 2020).

Notable exceptions to the top-down simulation models are Hovi et al. (2017) and Sprinz et al. (2018), who use agent-based models to describe bottom-up formation of a climate club. This covers lump-sum transfers and conditional commitments and sets reduction targets relative to countries' GDP.

We instead will examine a club with a carbon price as climate policy as it is easy to harmonize, has a starting point in the EU-ETS, limits carbon leakage within the club, and can be consistently complemented with a carbon border tariff.

3 Model

In this section we set up an agent-based model of the climate club, starting with an overview followed by a description of each model aspect.

3.1 Overview

The aim of this model is to study the evolution of climate clubs from their founding to their final stage. This is a complex and dynamic process, as it requires bottom-up cooperation between multiple heterogeneous actors with different economies, technologies and abatement costs. Because of this, we opt for an agent-based approach. Agent-based models (ABMs) have proven to be effective in modelling climate policies (Balint et al., 2017; Castro et al., 2020), especially when

combined with negotiation and coalition formation (Smead et al., 2014; Savin et al., 2023). The primary focus of the present model is on the growth process of the club.

We choose to only incorporate short-term costs and benefits and omit climate damages from our model, for two reasons. First, as argued by Gsottbauer and van den Bergh (2013), politicians are myopic in their decision making, both in general and in climate negotiations. This suggests that the decision to join a climate club is driven primarily by short-term effects. Second, estimates of climate damage have limited impact on national climate policy decisions when global cooperation is not yet enforced (see Section 2.5). The modelled short-term costs and benefits include: 1) loss of export due to BCA for non-members; 2) loss of export due to loss of competitiveness, 3) abatement costs and 4) BCA revenue for members of the club.

We define our climate club in line with Nordhaus (2015): we consider a harmonised carbon price as the climate policy instrument in the club. Regarding sanctions on non-members – and ensuring that imports are also subject to the climate policy of the club – we opt for a region-specific BCA, based on the implicit domestic carbon price in each non-member region. These BCAs can be set to match the carbon price of the club, so that both foreign and local suppliers pay similar prices within the club, or be set at a different level for additional punishment or leniency. We consider two options for distributing the revenue generated by BCA: 1) distribution among club members as additional club benefit, and 2) using the revenue as a fund to help over the abatement costs of potential members, which will lower the barrier to enter the club.

In line with the approach by Nordhaus (2015), we assume that countries outside the club do not retaliate against trade sanctions. Hence, countries do not impose counter-tariffs or change their trade partners due to the club sanctions. While there is discussion about how realistic this assumption is, there is general consensus that BCAs are less likely to trigger retaliation than general trade tariffs (Böhringer et al., 2022). Furthermore, this model uses agents with static data, including on CO₂ emissions. Change of emissions throughout the model is only due to the abatement actions taken by the climate club. We expect this assumption to not significantly affect the short- and medium-term evolution of the climate club.

We initialise the climate club with either one or two starting member(s). The decision to join or leave the club is made through a cost-benefit trade-off by each individual region. In the first decision round of the simulation, only non-members consider joining the club, while initial club members stay, even if the costs exceed benefits. This is attributed to a motivation factor, as we can assume that founding members will be particularly motivated to give the club a genuine opportunity, regardless of the short-term costs. In subsequent rounds, members also consider the option of leaving the club. The outcome of the analysis depends on the costs and benefits of each individual region, as well as the current state of the climate club. Any change in the climate club can alter costs and benefits and hence the outcome of region-specific trade-offs, which means it gives rise to a dynamic process. The process of joining and leaving is repeated until a stable coalition is formed. A coalition is considered stable when no region wants to join or leave it.

Each simulation run represents an experiment. We run the experiments with four varying experimental parameters: 1) the initial coalition, 2) the uniform carbon price of the club, 3) the stringency of the BCA, and 4) the allocation of BCA revenues. We are interested in comparing the different pathways for the climate club to grow from initial to stable coalition as well as the size and composition of the final coalitions.

3.2 Agents

The agents in this model comprise 31 relevant world regions, as illustrated in Figure 1. Of these, 22 represent single countries, while the remaining 9 regions are composed of a number of smaller countries. The countries within these regions collectively make a decision to join or leave the climate club. Aggregation was done taking into account geographical proximity, similarity of climate policy (represented by the implicit carbon price), and availability of data on abatement costs. We choose the regions in such a way that they cover sufficient carbon emissions to be relevant, have somewhat similar climate policies (i.e. implicit carbon price levels), and can be supported by region-specific data about abatement costs. The regions are heterogeneous and described by the following information:

1. GDP (Y ; World Bank, 2023).

2. Carbon dioxide emissions (\mathbf{E} ; Crippa et al., 2021).
3. Normalised implicit domestic carbon price (p_c): an estimate of the implicit domestic carbon price in each region, taking into account all existing climate policies (Narayanan et al., 2012).
4. Region-specific marginal abatement cost (MAC) curves: estimates of the MAC curves based on simulations with the POLES-Enerdata model (Enerdata, 2023).
5. Total export value (\mathbf{X}): the monetary value of all export flows from and to each region defined in the model (Gaulier and Zignago, 2010).
6. The relative export change due to BCA ($\delta_{\mathbf{X}}$): the relative change in export volume due to the introduction of a BCA (Larch and Wanner, 2017).

Data sources and further explanation of how data was obtained are provided in Section 4. An overview of the regions and their numerical data is given in Table 1.

Figure 1: Map of the 31 model regions. Red denotes single countries, labelled on the map, while other colors represent aggregated regions, with names listed in the legend. The constituents of the aggregated regions is listed in the supplementary materials.

3.3 The decision-making process by regions

Throughout the simulation each region evaluates yearly whether they should be part of the climate club. In each round of evaluations, non-members assess the costs and benefits of joining the club or remaining outside. Members perform in each period a similar assessment of whether they should leave or remain in the club. The assessment is done by comparing the net benefits, i.e. the benefits minus costs, of the two decisions: entering the club or staying outside. Countries then choose the option with the highest net benefit (or lowest net cost). Initial (founding) members stay in the club for at least two years before deciding whether to continue their membership or leave. We now discuss the equations for estimating the costs and benefits of each option. We omit the explicit notation of time in the equations; however, the variables described undergo temporal changes, reflecting the dynamic nature of the climate club, which evolves every round/year.

3.3.1 Cost of being outside the club

Cost of region-specific BCAs

Regions that remain outside or leave the climate club, and have a carbon price lower than the club's, will experience a loss in export revenue due to the Border Carbon Adjustment (BCA) imposed by the club. The club unilaterally sets the BCA, which can be higher, equal to, or lower than the club's carbon price, reflecting more stringent or lenient sanctions towards non-members. The BCA is the actual tax levied on imported carbon intensive goods. We operate under the assumption that non-members will not retaliate, so they do not generate extra import revenue. Staying outside the club is therefore only associated with costs and no benefits. The cost of staying outside the club for non-member n or the cost of leaving the club for member n (C_{out}^n) is given by:

$$C_{out}^n = \begin{cases} \tau_n \times \delta_X^{\prime n} \times X_{club}^n, & \text{if } p_c^{*club} \geq p_c^{*n}, \\ 0, & \text{if } p_c^{*club} < p_c^{*n}. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here p_c^{*n} is the current carbon price of region n and p_c^{*club} is the current carbon price of the club. Then we have the relative export change of n due to BCA $\delta_X^{\prime n}$, adjusted for the new carbon price of the club, and the total export from region n to the club X_{club}^n . The variable τ_n quantifies the club's attitude with respect to non-members, reflecting whether its approach is more punitive or conciliatory. It is defined as the ratio of the specific BCA for region n (t_c^n) to the carbon price of the club:

$$\tau_n = \frac{t_c^n}{p_c^{*club}}. \quad (2)$$

The specific BCA for region n is defined as:

$$t_c^n = \frac{p_c^{*club} - p_c^{*n}}{p_c^{*club} - p_c^{*min}} \times t_c^{club}. \quad (3)$$

The specific BCA for region n t_c^n is calculated by multiplying the BCA imposed by the club t_c^{club} by the difference between the carbon price of the club (p_c^{*club}) and the carbon price in region n (p_c^{*n}) divided by the difference between the carbon price of the club and the minimum carbon price of any region outside or inside the club (p_c^{*min}). This fraction can take a maximum value of 1 for the region with the lowest carbon price and a minimum value of 0 for regions that have already implemented the carbon price of the club. Therefore, there is only one region in each round that fully pays the BCA. Having a separate factor for the BCA allows us to model climate clubs with varying levels of stringency.

The relative export change of n due to BCA adjusted for the new carbon price of the club $\delta_X^{\prime n}$ is calculated as follows:

$$\delta_X^{\prime n} = \frac{p_c^{*club}}{p_c^n} \times \delta_X^n. \quad (4)$$

The relative export change of n due to BCA δ_X^n is calibrated to the original (implicit) carbon price of n , p_c^n (Larch and Wanner, 2017) and, therefore, we need to adjust it for the new carbon price. For simplicity, we use a linear relation for the carbon price elasticity of export value. However, we acknowledge that we might also use a non-linear elasticity.

Although the carbon price and BCA are related, they do not cause the same effect. Increasing carbon price within the club, translates into a larger carbon price difference and thus cost of remaining outside the club for non-member n . However, the raised carbon price also affects the club members through the loss of competitiveness due to rising production costs. A higher t_c^{club} also increases the cost of staying out for n , but does not affect production costs within the club. It allows the club to put more pressure on non-members, without raising its own production costs. Additionally, increasing the carbon price raises entry costs in the form of higher abatement costs when joining. This is not the case when increasing t_c^{club} . The value of t_c^{club} will be adjusted across experiments to reflect different levels of stringency in the penalties imposed by the club on non-members.

Equation 1 yields the total cost of staying out or leaving the club (C_{out}^n), which is the absolute change in export value for region n , based on the current carbon price of the club and the BCA imposed on non-members. If the carbon price of a region n is equal or higher than the carbon price of the club, $C_{out}^n = 0$. In addition to this, regions inside the club only face a cost for leaving in their first round as club members, as they are still in the process of implementing the carbon price of the club. From their second round as club members on, $C_{out}^n = 0$. Furthermore, if the climate club comprises only one member n , the cost of leaving the club for that member – even in the first round – is $C_{out}^n = 0$, as the club would no longer exist if n leaves.

Cost of uniform BCA

Although a region-specific BCA seems to be more fair and could motivate regions outside the club to elevate their domestic carbon prices and reduce their domestic CO₂ emissions, concerns arise regarding its compliance with World Trade Organization (WTO) rules (Pauwelyn and Kleimann, 2020; Lim et al., 2021; Böhringer et al., 2022). As explained by Böhringer et al. (2022), the scope of application in adherence to WTO obligations would limit the environmental reach of BCAs. Fortunately, there are exceptions in WTO regulation which could permit a region-specific BCA (see Section 2.3).

Nevertheless, it is pertinent to contemplate situations where such an approach might not be feasible and alignment with WTO rules becomes mandatory. To ensure the BCA’s compatibility with the WTO, countries’ scope of adjustment should be consistent with the scope of domestic carbon price application. This means that a uniform BCA must be applied to non-members, equivalent to the carbon price of the club. Under this scenario, both international and local suppliers would be paying similar prices for goods marketed within the club. Exemptions from the BCA would only be permissible for regions with domestic carbon prices matching or exceeding that of the club (Sapir, 2021; Böhringer et al., 2022).

In this scenario, the BCA imposed by the club is the same for every non-member with a carbon price lower than the one within the club. Further to this, if following the WTO guidelines, the BCA shall be equivalent to the carbon price of the club. Consequently, $t_c^n = t_c^{club} = p_c^{*club}$. Therefore, in every simulation following WTO rules’, the variable τ_n in the cost of staying out equation (Eq. 1) becomes:

$$\tau = \frac{t_c^{club}}{p_c^{*club}} = 1 \quad (5)$$

3.3.2 Cost of being in the club

Abatement costs

Non-members wishing to join and members wishing to stay must adhere to the climate policy of the club. In our model, this means implementing or raising the domestic carbon price to the level of the club. Raising the carbon price induces abatement, up to the point where the marginal abatement cost (MAC) is equal to the club’s carbon price. The MAC tends to increase the more emissions are reduced as emitters run out of cheap options to reduce emissions. It varies between countries; differences in sectoral structures in terms of industrial, agricultural and other activities lead to different carbon intensities and varying transition costs. Differential access to energy sources, renewable energy technologies and abatement technologies affect the availability and cost of abatement policies. This is captured through country-specific MAC curves. To use MAC curves as an approximation for abatement costs, we assume non-members follow a cost-minimizing strategy in reducing emissions. This means they implement abatement policies in order of their marginal abatement cost. The total cost of the induced abatement for region n (C_a^n) can be calculated by integrating the area beneath the MAC curve from current level of emissions (e^n) to the level of emissions achieved by implementing the carbon price of the club (e^{club}):

$$C_a^n = \int_{e^n}^{e^{club}} MAC^n(e). \quad (6)$$

The MAC curve links the effectiveness of abatement options to their cost by taking abatement of emissions (e) as input and providing the carbon price needed for additional marginal abatement as output. We assume regions have already implemented all policies that cost less than the current carbon price because of the cost-minimizing strategy. We therefore take the level of emissions at the current carbon price (e^n) as our lower bound. The level of emissions at the carbon price of the club (e^{club}) is the upper bound.

To illustrate the cost of joining, we consider a numerical example for Brazil. The MAC curve of Brazil is shown in Figure 2. The implicit carbon price of Brazil is 22.06 USD/tCO₂, as marked by the horizontal line. We assume Brazil has implemented all abatement options that cost less than this carbon price before joining the club. This means it has already reduced 8.8 MtCO₂. When Brazil joins a climate club with a carbon price of 100 USD/tCO₂ (horizontal line), it implements all remaining abatement options with a cost up to this price. This means it further reduces emissions by $34.7 - 8.8 = 25.9$ MtCO₂ when joining the club. The cost of this reduction is calculated by integrating the curve in Figure 2 from 8.8 MtCO₂ to 34.7 MtCO₂ (shaded area), which equals 1528 million USD.

Figure 2: Estimated MAC curve for Brazil, fitted to data from the POLES-Enerdata model. Mentioned points from the numerical example are marked with dashed lines. The shaded blue section is the integral of the MAC curve, representing the total abatement cost of joining the club.

In the model, during the first year of membership, countries are in the process of adopting the carbon price of the club, which implies they still have to cope with abatement costs. From the second year onwards as a club member, if the carbon price of the club remains constant, $C_{abatement}^n = 0$. Within the model structure, once the carbon price of the club is reached, there is no economic motivation to further abate emissions. If a region, having already adopted abatement measures to meet the club’s constant carbon price, decides to leave the club and later decides to rejoin it, it will not incur additional abatement costs.

The MAC curves integrated in Eq. 6 are generated using data from Enerdata’s long-term Marginal Abatement Cost Curves (MACCs) (Enerdata, 2023; Section 4.3). The currency values from this source is given in 2015-USD and, consequently, the abatement costs C_a^n calculated using this data are also in 2015-USD. However, the other costs and benefits computed in this model are in 2021-USD, derived from the export data provided by the CEPII BACI dataset (Gaulier and Zignago, 2010). Therefore, the abatement costs require an adjustment to account for the USD inflation rate between 2015 and 2021. As per the United States Bureau of Labor Statistics (2023) data, 1 USD in 2015 holds an equivalent value of 1.1433 USD in 2021.

Cost of loss of competitiveness

After joining, non-members must adhere to the carbon price of the carbon club. Higher carbon prices cause an increase in production costs. This leads to a loss of competitiveness when exporting goods outside the club. As a result, part of the production of goods intended for countries outside the club is moved to regions with lower production costs. We approximate the value of lost export by considering a hypothetical BCA on region n ’s exports to outside of the club. This hypothetical BCA is levied by n itself, adjusting for the difference between n ’s original (implicit) carbon price and the current carbon price of the club. We approximate the value of the loss of competitiveness as:

$$C_c^n = \begin{cases} \delta_X'^n \times X_{row}^n \times S_X^{club}, & \text{if } \exists \text{ region } i \mid p_c^i < p_c^{club}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

If there are regions with a carbon price lower than the carbon price of the club, as stipulated by condition 1 in Eq. 7, being inside the club will bear a competitive disadvantage. In this case, the first term $\delta_x'^n$ is the relative export change of n due to BCA, adjusted to the carbon price of the club (Eq. 4). We multiply this relative change by the total export of non-member n to outside the club X_{row}^n (rest of world). Since there is no loss of competitiveness within the club, we only consider export to the rest of the world. Finally, we account for the size of the climate club relative to the world (S_X^{club}). Although higher production costs cause production of goods to be moved to regions with lower carbon prices, the potential to move production is finite. We assume this potential depends on the size of the climate club. If the club is responsible for a small portion of the worlds exports, there is lot of potential to move production elsewhere. When the club controls nearly all export, moving production becomes limited by the barriers listed before. Therefore, we model the loss of competitiveness to scale inversely with club size, such that:

$$S_X^{club} = \frac{X_{row}}{X_{world}}, \quad (8)$$

where X_{row} is the value of the total export towards the rest of the world (or total imports of the rest of the world), both from the club to the rest of the world and from the rest of the world to itself. We divide this by the total export of the world (X_{world}). This gives us the value of export going outside the club, relative to total export of the world, which is the inverse of the export value going inside the club. As more countries join the club, the value of export to outside the club decreases and S_X^{club} goes from 1 to 0, therefore decreasing the loss of competitiveness of club members. When evaluating the cost of joining the club for a non-member, S_X^{club} is recalculated to reflect the potential club size upon their entry.

Moreover, if all regions, members and non-members of the club, have or implement a carbon price at least as high as the carbon price of the club, relocating production to regions outside the club will not result in a reduction in production costs. Consequently, regardless of the size of the club, being a member does not lead to a competitiveness disadvantage, leading to $C_c^n = 0$ (condition 2 in Eq. 7).

We can estimate the total cost of joining for non-member n (C_{in}^n) by adding the costs of the loss of competitiveness and abatement (considering the situation where relocating production to regions with lower production costs is possible):

$$C_{in}^n = C_c^n + C_a^n = \delta_X'^n \times X_{row}^n \times S_X^{club} + \int_{e^n}^{e^{club}} MAC^n(e). \quad (9)$$

3.3.3 Benefits of being in the club - Use of BCA revenues

Members of the club receive revenue generated by the BCA imposed on non-members. The total BCA revenue of the club (R) is equal to the collective BCA payments by all non-members. This revenue can be distributed in several ways. First, the revenue can remain with the countries that levied the BCA, distributed among them proportional to the share of exports from non-members to members of the club. The benefits of joining for non-member n and the benefits of staying inside the club for member n (B_{in}^n ; in stands for “in the club”) are then given by:

$$B_{in}^n = \sum_{i \neq n} S_t^{n,i} C_{out}^i, \quad (10)$$

where $S_t^{n,i}$ is the share of the total BCA costs of non-member i (which stays outside the club) that is paid to (potential) member n , i.e. the share of export from non-member i to member n . C_{out}^i is the cost of staying out of the club for non-member i . Summing over the BCA revenue flows from all non-members i - except for n - gives the total revenue of (potential) member n .

Second, the revenue can be equally distributed among all club members. For a potential member of the club, the benefit of joining would be:

$$B_{in}^n = \frac{1}{n_m + 1} R = \frac{1}{n_m + 1} \sum_{i \neq n} C_{out}^i, \quad (11)$$

where $n_m + 1$ refers to the number of club members if region n joins the club. The sum goes through all non-members except for n , as region n would not be paying BCA if joining the club and, therefore, it would not be contributing to the generation of revenue. The revenue for a member of the club is calculated as:

$$B_{in}^n = \frac{1}{n_m} R = \frac{1}{n_m} \sum_i C_{out}^i, \quad (12)$$

where n_m represents the current number of members of the club and i represents all non-members.

Another option that is considered in literature is BCA “revenue recycling” (Shaw and Fu, 2020). With this approach, countries impose a BCA, but return part of the revenue to exporting non-members. This offers the advantage of reducing the risk of trade retaliation, while still addressing the climate externality in non-members. In our model, revenues returned to potential new members of the club, i.e. non-members, are specifically earmarked for investment in abatement policies to reduce national CO₂ emissions. In this scenario, the recycled revenue can also be considered a benefit of joining the club, as it will reduce the abatement costs associated with implementing the its carbon price. If following this strategy, after each round of negotiations, the part of the revenue returned to non-members is distributed proportional to their potential membership abatement costs. The rest of the revenue is divided between club members proportional to the share of exports from non-members to members of the club. For potential member n , the abatement costs in the next round of negotiation would be reduced by the following amount:

$$B_a^n = \beta \times R \times \left[C_{in}^n / \sum_p C_{in}^p \right]. \quad (13)$$

Here R is the total BCA revenue of the club. The term $C_{in}^n / \sum_p C_{in}^p$ gives the proportional weight of the abatement costs of potential member n , relative to the total abatement cost of all potential members p . Furthermore, the distribution variable β is introduced, which reflects the portion of the revenue returned to non-members to assist them in reducing their abatement costs. The remaining fraction of the revenue, $1 - \beta$, stays with club members and is distributed proportionally based on their share of exports (Eq. 16). The β distribution variable is defined as a value between 0 and 1 proportional to the size of the club (S_X^{club} , see Eq. 8), i.e. the larger the club the smaller the share of revenue returned to non-members:

$$\beta = \alpha \times S_X^{club}, \quad (14)$$

where parameter α is an input variable, defined between 0 and 1, reflecting whether the club is willing to return a smaller or larger share of the revenue. The abatement costs for potential member n after a round of negotiations would therefore become:

$$C_a^{n'} = C_a^n - B_a^n = \int_{e^n}^{e^{club}} MAC^n(e) - \beta \times R \times \left[C_{in}^n / \sum_p C_{in}^p \right]. \quad (15)$$

The remaining benefits for club members - and benefits of joining for potential members - are:

$$B_{in}^n = (1 - \beta) \times R^n = (1 - \beta) \times \sum_{i \neq n} S_t^{n,i} C_{out}^i. \quad (16)$$

3.3.4 The decision to join

Having described both the costs of joining and staying out, as well as the benefits of joining, we can combine the equations to form a condition to join the club. A non-member will join the club if the net costs of joining are lower than the net costs of staying out (C_{out}^n). The net cost of joining is given by the cost of joining (C_{in}^n) minus the benefits of joining (B_{in}^n). These benefits depend on the scenario considered in the experiment: 1) BCA equally distributed among members 2) BCA

distributed among club members according to the share of exports from non-members to members of the club or 3) part of the BCA revenue is split among new members to cover a proportional part of their abatement costs. Since we do not consider any benefits for staying outside the club, the net costs of staying out are simply C_{out}^n . A non-member n will thus join the club if:

$$B_{in}^n > C_{in}^n - C_{out}^n. \quad (17)$$

For instance, in a scenario where (1) BCA revenue is distributed among club members based on their share of exports, (2) there are non-members with a carbon price lower than the carbon price of the club, and (3) $p_c^{*club} \geq p_c^{*n}$, i.e. substituting Eqs. 1, 6, 7 and 10, the decision rule for non-member n to join the club is given by:

$$\sum_{i \neq n} S_t^{n,i} C_{out}^i > \delta_X'^n \times X_{row}^n \times S_X^{club} + \int_{e^n}^{e^{club}} MAC^n(e) - \tau_n \times \delta_X'^n \times X_{club}^n, \quad (18)$$

where i represents all non-members.

3.3.5 The decision to leave

The decision to leave or stay inside the club for club members is developed through an analogous procedure. A member n will leave the club if:

$$B_{in}^n < C_{in}^n - C_{out}^n. \quad (19)$$

As per the specifications set in Eq. 18, this condition translates to:

$$\sum_i S_t^{n,i} C_{out}^i < \delta_X'^n \times X_{row}^n \times S_X^{club} + \int_{e^n}^{e^{club}} MAC^n(e) - \tau_n \times \delta_X'^n \times X_{club}^n, \quad (20)$$

where i represents all non-members.

4 Data

In this section we describe the data used in this model. We highlight the sources, calibration process and aggregation of the regions.

4.1 Overview of sources

In this study we combine data from a number of sources. Total GDP (Y) from each region is taken from the World Bank (2023) for the year 2021. Exports data (X) for each region in 2021 (in 2021-USD) is provided by the CEPII BACI dataset (Gaulier and Zignago, 2010). Values for the CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels (E) per country are extracted from Crippa et al. (2021) for the year 2020. Estimates of the implicit domestic carbon price (λ) are provided by the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) 8 database (Narayanan et al., 2012) for the year 2007 (2007-USD). Normalisation is done to correct for negative carbon prices (essentially carbon subsidies) by scaling the prices between one for the lowest carbon price (Malaysia, with -13.12 USD) and the maximum carbon price found in the 31 aggregated regions of the model (Norway, with 138.42 USD):

$$p_c = \frac{\lambda - \lambda_{min}}{\lambda_{max} - \lambda_{min}} (\lambda_{max} - 1) + 1, \quad (21)$$

where p_c denotes the normalised carbon price.

Larch and Wanner (2017) provide values per country for the percentage change in trade flows due to the introduction of BCAs (δ_X). These values are extrapolated from a model that assumes the introduction of carbon tariffs that equalize the differences in the levels of the implicit carbon taxes by Narayanan et al. (2012). For each region-pair the region with the higher implicit carbon tax imposes a tariff on imported goods from the other region. The larger the difference between two regions' carbon taxes, the higher is the carbon tariff imposed by the high-price region. Trade flows decrease in all countries, with a value range between 5.9% for Azerbaijan and 0.66% for Sweden (Figure 3). The overall reduction in world trade flows is by 1.9 percent.

Figure 3: Percentage changes in trade flows due to the counterfactual introduction of carbon tariffs (δ_X). Source: Larch and Wanner (2017).

4.2 Regions

Out of the 31 regions in our model, 22 represent single countries. For these countries, data can be extracted directly from the sources named in Section 4.1. Data of the nine remaining regions needs to be aggregated. GDP and export values of constituent regions can simply be added to obtain the total GDP and export of the region. The implicit carbon prices and the changes in trade flows are aggregated using a weighted average. We use the world share of CO₂ emissions of each country as weights to calculate the averages of these variables for the aggregated regions. An overview of the regions data is given in Table 1.

4.3 MAC curves

The MAC curves are generated with data from Enerdata’s long-term Marginal Abatement Cost Curves (MACCs, Enerdata, 2023). The curves are simulated by running the POLES model under different scenarios, with different carbon prices (in 2015-USD). The POLES model is a global energy forecasting model that is used by policymakers, researchers, and business analysts to assess climate policies, evaluate cost and efficiency, and simulate carbon markets. The MACCs show the different levels of emission reductions that can be achieved at various carbon price levels in a given year, country, and sector. The results of these simulations are then plotted on a graph, with the emission reductions on the y-axis and the carbon price on the x-axis. The POLES-Enerdata simulations are developed for different years: 2025, 2030, 2040 and 2050.

Table 1: Overview of all 31 regions and their corresponding data. The emissions data (E) are given in relation to the total world emissions (35,963 Mtons). The cumulative emissions share in this table amount to 97.05%, the rest is attributed to international aviation (0.94%) and international shipping (2.13%).

Region	Acronym	E (%)	Y (M USD)	λ (USD/tCO ₂)	p_c (USD/tCO ₂)	δ_X (%)	X (M USD)
China	CHN	32.48	17,734,063	4.35	16.84	-1.22	1,857,603
United States	USA	12.61	23,315,081	13.92	25.52	-0.92	2,617,533
EU + other countries	EU+	7.75	17,844,392	69.92	76.31	-1.41	2,272,129
India	IND	6.71	3,176,295	16.81	28.14	-1.5	557,448
Russia	RUS	4.66	1,778,783	22	32.85	-1.73	267,224
Middle East	ME	4.29	1,829,169	4.26	16.76	-3.2	531,298
Japan	JPN	2.95	4,940,878	41.75	50.76	-0.81	675,970
Rest of South-East Asia	XSE	1.91	1,334,168	10.56	22.47	-1.22	1,092,614
South Korea	KOR	1.73	1,810,956	17.34	28.62	-0.95	558,184
Saudi Arabia	SAU	1.64	833,541	-0.03	12.87	-3.74	149,528
North Africa	NAF	1.62	799,558	0.05	12.95	-3.76	207,821
Rest of CIS	CIS	1.59	497,870	4.23	16.73	-3.15	119,039
Indonesia	IDN	1.58	1,186,093	1.88	14.60	-1.64	189,087
Canada	CAN	1.51	1,988,336	30.51	40.56	-1.02	475,173
Rest of America	XAM	1.26	1,982,627	18.29	29.48	-1.34	326,794
Brazil	BRA	1.26	1,608,981	22.06	32.90	-0.92	222,409
Pacific	PAC	1.22	1,862,769	1.02	13.82	-1.61	277,619
South Africa	SAF	1.21	419,015	8.35	20.47	-1.66	92,056
Mexico	MEX	1.13	1,272,839	-0.15	12.76	-1.57	446,012
Turkey	TUR	1.13	819,035	89.49	94.05	-2.1	230,692
Rest of Africa	XAF	1.06	1,499,650	6.89	19.15	-2.43	305,959
Rest of South Asia	XSA	1.06	912,476	22.31	33.13	-1.88	232,660
Vietnam	VNM	0.9	366,138	-4.19	9.1	-2.19	313,021
United Kingdom	UK	0.87	3,131,378	92.31	96.61	-0.95	656,123
Malaysia	MYS	0.73	372,981	-13.12	1	-2.94	228,898
Thailand	THA	0.71	505,947	13.03	24.72	-1.13	242,939
Ukraine	UKR	0.53	200,086	15.14	26.63	-2.69	73,564
Argentina	ARG	0.49	487,227	28.84	39.05	-1.17	60,039
Chile	CHL	0.24	317,059	35	44.64	-1.2	87,126
Norway	NOR	0.12	482,174	138.42	138.42	-1.34	94,617
Switzerland	CHE	0.1	800,640	75.84	81.67	-0.85	281,693

5 Results

In this section, we present the outcomes of our simulations, each representing a different scenario characterized by a combination of variations in the following parameters:

- *Initial coalition of the club*: we explore three scenarios – a small initial climate club consisting of Switzerland, a medium initial climate club consisting of the EU and other European countries (EU+) and a large initial climate club consisting of the US and the EU+. The first case is motivated by our intention to evaluate the potential for a small nation such as Switzerland, with an ambitious climate change mitigation agenda, to unilaterally initiate a climate club. Additionally, we aim to analyze the performance of larger regions initiating a climate coalition. Different starting coalitions matter as the larger the initial climate club the higher the costs for non-members to stay out, and the greater the benefits of joining due to increased BCA revenue. The scenario with a club initiated by a large coalition with the US and the EU+ is also relevant because these regions hold a significant global influence together and, therefore, a coalition initiated by them could further constrain the risk of retaliation by other countries.
- *Carbon price of the club*: we consider three possible carbon prices in each simulation – 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂. These values were selected in relation to ranges of estimates of the Social Costs of Carbon (SCC, see Section 2.5), using rounded numbers for clarity. The lowest carbon

price, 50 USD/tCO₂, aligns with the SCC estimated mean value of 51 USD/tCO₂ developed by the United States’ Inter-agency Working Group (IWG) on Social Cost of Greenhouse Gases. This SCC value has been employed by the US government for various purposes, including assessing the impact of numerous regulations as well as serving as the basis for proposals for federal carbon tax legislation (Carleton and Greenstone, 2021; IWG, 2021; Rennert et al., 2022). A more ambitious carbon price, 200 USD/tCO₂, matches the SCC recently estimated by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA, 2022) and the GIVE model estimations by Rennert et al. (2022). The EPA has proposed to increase the IWG estimated SCC value to 190 USD/tCO₂. Rennert et al. (2022) estimate a similar price, 185 USD/tCO₂, with a range of prices between 44 and 413 USD/tCO₂, which align with the lowest (50 USD/tCO₂) and highest (400 USD/tCO₂) carbon prices in our simulations. The upper limit of this SCC range corresponds to a scenario of high damages and a low discount rate, meeting concerns expressed by many authors about fat tails in damage uncertainty and ethics about discounting the future (Hepburn and Beckerman, 2007; Weitzman, 2014).

- *Level of the BCA*: we adjust the BCAs to three distinct levels relative to the carbon prices. The first is 50% below the carbon price, which represents a lenient strategy towards non-members. This aims to circumvent potential sanctions while offering some protection to the carbon price in place within the club on domestically produced goods. The second level involves a BCA equal to the carbon price of the club – a symmetric strategy – resulting in similar carbon price on imports and domestically produced goods within the club. Lastly, setting the BCA at 50% above the carbon price acts as a punitive strategy, intensifying the incentive for non-members to become part of the club and providing additional protection to the climate policy of the club.
- *Use of BCA revenues*: we implement four scenarios for use of the tariff revenue. In the first, the revenue is equally shared among club members. In the second, revenue stays with the countries that have levied the tariffs – i.e. revenues are distributed according to the countries’ share of exports. In the third scenario, a portion of the revenue is returned to potential new members to cover part of their abatement costs, while the rest is distributed among club members according to the share of exports from non-members to members of the club. Variable α in Eq. 14 is set at $\alpha = 0.5$, denoting that less than half of the revenue is returned to potential members. In the fourth scenario, most of the revenue is used to cover abatement costs of potential members, while the remaining is distributed among club members according to the share of exports from non-members to members of the club. To implement this, variable α is set at $\alpha = 1$.

In addition to the previous scenarios with region-specific BCAs, adapted to the implicit domestic carbon price in each region, we explore the scenario where adherence to WTO obligations is unavoidable. In this case, the climate club applies a uniform BCA, equivalent to the carbon price of the club (Equation 5). We consider that the BCA revenue stays with the countries that have levied the tariffs – i.e. distribution according to the share of exports. This is evaluated using the same initial coalitions of Switzerland, EU+, and US and EU+, and club carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂. In each simulation, the BCA is set to match the respective carbon price.

Our model encompasses a comprehensive set of scenarios. With combinations of 3 initial coalitions, 3 carbon prices and BCA levels, and 4 methods of revenue distribution, plus the additional variations with uniform BCA – 3 initial regions and 3 carbon prices – we conducted a total of 117 simulations. Table 2 provides an overview of the simulation outcomes. We illustrate a few representative examples in subsequent sections. The detailed outcomes of all simulations can be found in the [Appendix: Additional results](#).

Overall, the club has a high likelihood of achieving global coverage, with 79 out of 117 (67.5%) tested scenarios leading to full membership. When a climate club is initiated by a large or medium-sized group of countries, the prospects of reaching full membership increase to 63 out of 78 (80.8%) tested scenarios. Furthermore, 69 out of 81 simulations (85.2%) lead to a global climate club when the club adopts a symmetric or punitive strategy, which ensures higher benefits for the club through the distribution of BCA revenues. By combining the two conditions, i.e. a medium or large region

starting a climate club with a BCA equal to or higher than the carbon price of the club, we find that 52 out of 54 (96.3%) tested scenarios result in a club with global coverage.

In addition, if we consider scenarios where a high carbon price is implemented (≥ 200 USD/tCO₂), which could lead to a significant reduction in global CO₂ emissions, full membership is also achieved in the majority of scenarios, namely 62.8% (49 out of 78). This percentage significantly increases to 97.2% (35 out of 36 tested scenarios) if the high carbon price club adopts a symmetric or punitive strategy and is initiated by a medium or large region.

Table 2: Overview of simulation outcomes for various combinations of initial club, carbon price (CP), border carbon adjustment (BCA) and use of BCA revenue, in USD/tCO₂. Numbers in green represent a full club (31 members), and in red an empty club (no members) by the end of the simulation. Each cell displays: the number of rounds (years) taken to reach convergence; number of participants in the final club; percentage of CO₂ emissions covered by the final club.

Initial club	CP	BCA	Equal distribution	Share of exports	Return BCA revenue ($\alpha = 0.5$)	Return BCA revenue ($\alpha = 1$)	Uniform BCA ¹
			Info: Rounds to convergence; Final club size; % CO ₂ emissions within final club				
CHE	50	25	2; 4; 1%	2; 2; 0.6%	2; 1; 0.1%	3; 0; 0%	4; 31; 100%
	50	50	6; 31; 100%	5; 31; 100%	2; 2; 0.6%	3; 0; 0%	
	50	75	5; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	5; 31; 100%	3; 0; 0%	
	200	100	2; 4; 1%	2; 2; 0.2%	2; 1; 0.1%	3; 0; 0%	
	200	200	14; 0; 0%	5; 31; 100%	2; 2; 0.2%	3; 0; 0%	
	200	300	5; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	5; 31; 100%	3; 0; 0%	
	400	200	2; 4; 1%	2; 2; 0.2%	2; 1; 0.1%	3; 0; 0%	
	400	400	7; 19; 20.5%	5; 31; 100%	2; 2; 0.2%	3; 0; 0%	
	400	600	5; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	6; 31; 100%	3; 0; 0%	
EU+	50	25	4; 31; 100%	5; 31; 100%	6; 31; 100%	3; 0; 0%	3; 31; 100%
	50	50	3; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	4; 0; 0%	
	50	75	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	
	200	100	8; 0; 0%	11; 0; 0%	5; 31; 100%	4; 0; 0%	
	200	200	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	5; 31; 100%	
	200	300	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	
	400	200	9; 0; 0%	7; 10; 16.6%	7; 31; 100%	4; 0; 0%	
	400	400	3; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	4; 0; 0%	
	400	600	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	5; 31; 100%	
EU+ & USA	50	25	3; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	7; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%
	50	50	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	
	50	75	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	
	200	100	7; 0; 0%	10; 0; 0%	4; 31; 100%	4; 0; 0%	
	200	200	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	
	200	300	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	
	400	200	7; 0; 0%	9; 0; 0%	6; 31; 100%	4; 0; 0%	
	400	400	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	4; 31; 100%	
	400	600	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	3; 31; 100%	

¹ In this scenario, as explained in Section 3.3.1, the BCA is always equal to the carbon price of the club. Therefore, only three simulations are undertaken for each initial club.

5.1 BCA revenues remains within the club

In the simulations where BCA revenue remains within the club, it is distributed either equally among club members or proportionally to the share of exports from non-members to members of the club. In both scenarios, we can observe a majority of simulations ending up with full membership (29/45 simulations, see Table 2). Notably, simulations featuring carbon prices in line with current estimations of SCC and with potential to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions, CP = 200 and 400 USD/tCO₂, show promise. This is particularly true when paired with a similar or higher BCA, with full membership achieved in 22 out of 24 tested scenarios.

To illustrate, a climate club created by Switzerland, which equally shares BCA revenue among club members (Figure 4), succeeds in getting all regions to join the club in four out of nine simulations. This scenario showcases the feasibility of the climate-club approach to achieve global coverage, even when initiated by a region only responsible for 0.1% of global CO₂ emissions. The best outcomes are achieved when opting for a punitive strategy, setting the BCA 50% higher than the carbon price of the club. In these three simulations, all regions join the club within five rounds. Conversely, adopting a lenient strategy with BCAs set 50% below the carbon price proves less effective, attracting only four regions that together account for less than 1% of emissions. When the club is initiated by Switzerland, and revenue is distributed among club members according to the share of exports into the club, the success of the club is higher. In this case, six out of nine simulations end up with full membership, for both punitive and symmetric strategies.

Figure 4: Climate-club dynamics with Switzerland as the initial member, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for BCA revenue equally shared among club members. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

When expanding our focus to medium and large climate clubs, including the EU+, and the USA together with the EU+, consistent trends emerge. Both symmetric and punitive strategies result in full membership within three or four rounds, irrespective of the revenue distribution mechanism among club members. However, a lenient strategy, particularly with higher carbon prices, yields less favorable outcomes, often resulting in partial or no membership after multiple rounds. Lenient strategies only lead to full membership with a medium-sized or large initial climate club if combined

with a low carbon price (50 USD/tCO₂).

5.2 BCA revenues cover abatement costs of potential members

In simulations where a portion of the BCA revenue is returned to potential members to cover part of their abatement costs, the outcomes vary significantly depending on the quantity of revenue returned (value of α in Eq. 14) and the size of the initial climate club. In the illustrative example in Figure 5, we have a climate club initiated by the EU+ and the United States (large initial club) that returns a substantial part of the club’s revenue to non-members ($\alpha = 1$). As defined by Equation 14, the initial club transfers most of the revenue and, as the club expands, the amount of revenue returned decreases. Seven out of nine simulations result in full membership, and the remaining two end up when the club empties. Both punitive and symmetric strategies motivate all regions to join the club within three or four rounds. However, a lenient strategy only works if combined with a low carbon price (50 USD/tCO₂).

Figure 5: Climate-club dynamics with the US and the EU+ as initial members, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for part of BCA revenue returned to non-members to cover abatement costs – $\alpha = 1$. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

In the case of a small initial climate club, led by Switzerland, returning a major part of the revenue to potential members, all simulations result in an empty club (Table 2). Regions outside the club have little motivation to join due to a combination of low benefits of being in and an insufficient coverage of abatement costs. Finally, if a medium-sized club created by the EU+ returns a big part of the BCA revenue to non-members, the club will only succeed if following a punitive strategy or a symmetric strategy with a CP = 200 USD/tCO₂ (full membership reached in 4 out of 9 simulations).

If the amount of revenue returned is smaller – less than half of it, i.e. $\alpha = 0.5$ in Eq. 14 – the results look more promising. A small initial climate club, led by Switzerland, can succeed if adopting a punitive strategy, after five or six rounds. Conversely, lenient or symmetric strategies

initiated by this small region tend to attract only a limited number of participants, with final clubs that account for less than 1% of global CO₂ emissions. However, if the club is launched by a medium-sized (EU+) or large set of regions (US and EU+), every simulation leads to full membership. Convergence time is shorter when there is a large initial coalition and punitive or symmetric strategies are followed.

In light of these results, three main findings can be drawn regarding strategies for a successful climate club formation. First, the simulations where a part of the BCA revenue is returned to potential members underscore the importance of the initial club’s size. A small initiating region like Switzerland is insufficient to form a successful club in most scenarios where a part of the revenue is returned. Second, the results reveal that a club initiated by a medium-sized or large coalition, which returns a portion – less than half – of the revenues to potential members for abatement costs, consistently achieves full membership in all tested scenarios. This includes scenarios with a high carbon price in place (≥ 200 USD/tCO₂). Third, overcompensating non-members – returning a majority of the revenue – can negatively impact the formation of a global climate club by significantly diminishing club benefits and, therefore, reducing the motivation to join the club. This can be observed in the simulations where the EU+ is the starting region, as full membership outcomes go down from 9 out of 9 simulations to 4 out of 9 when returning a larger share of the revenue.

5.3 WTO rules

The simulations in this subsection explore the scenario where the strategy of adhering to WTO Article XX concerning General Exceptions is not possible and, therefore, the club has to respect the WTO non-discriminatory principles (see Section 2.3). In this case, the climate club applies a uniform BCA (Equation 5), equal to the carbon price of the club. Regions outside the club are now required to pay the full BCA, irrespective of their implicit domestic carbon prices (unless they exceed the club’s carbon price). This results in a higher cost of staying outside the club and a greater benefit of joining. As a consequence, full membership is achieved in all scenarios (Figure 6). Convergence time is shorter, three rounds, when the initial club is medium (EU+) or large (EU+ and US). If the club is initiated by Switzerland, full membership is achieved after four rounds – when CP and BCA = 50 USD/tCO₂ – or five rounds – when CP and BCA = 200 USD/tCO₂ or CP and BCA = 400 USD/tCO₂.

While this approach yields positive outcomes in terms of costs and benefits, it faces several constraints that diminish its viability compared to the other CO₂ emission reduction strategies presented in this paper. A uniform BCA implies an unfair treatment of regions with high domestic carbon prices in place. In our simulations, for example, when CP = 200 or 400 USD/tCO₂, both Norway, with a normalized implicit carbon price of 138.42 USD/tCO₂, and Malaysia, with a normalized implicit carbon price of 1 USD/tCO₂, bear the same BCA costs when exporting to the climate club. Such unfair treatment could complicate the implementation of a high BCA and carbon price, limiting its environmental reach, and trigger retaliatory responses from countries with high carbon prices in place. Furthermore, it may lower the incentive for countries outside the club to elevate their domestic carbon prices or implement other ambitious climate policies, as an intermediate step before joining the club. The only way for regions reluctant to join the club to lower BCA export costs would be to reduce exports to climate club regions (Böhringer et al., 2022). This would however become more complicated if the club expands.

Figure 6: Climate-club dynamics with Switzerland, the EU+, and the US and the EU+ as initial members, for carbon prices and uniform BCAs of 50 USD/tCO₂ (light blue), 200 USD/tCO₂ (blue), and 400 USD/tCO₂ (dark blue). BCA revenue remains within the club, distributed according to the share of exports.

6 Discussion and conclusions

Our objective in this paper was to identify the likelihood of, and feasible pathways and conditions for, a climate club of countries to develop into a full, ambitious and effective climate agreement. To this end, we developed a dynamic agent-based model that describes the evolution of a climate club from its implementation to its final stage. The model comprises 31 global regions that decide to join or leave the club based on trading off relevant costs and benefits. The simulated climate club is initiated by small (Switzerland), medium (EU+) or large (US and EU+) regions that implement a uniform carbon price and a border carbon adjustment (BCA) on non-members. The carbon price of the club was set at three different levels – 50, 200 and 400 USD/tCO₂ – based on estimations of the Social Cost of Carbon. The BCA could mirror the carbon price of the club (a symmetric strategy), be 50% below the carbon price (representing a lenient strategy towards non-members) or be 50% above it (implying a punitive strategy towards non-members).

The simulation results indicate that achieving global coverage of the club, thereby harmonising and enabling ambitious climate policy, is an attainable objective in 67.5% of all tested scenarios (79 out of 117). When the climate club is initiated by a medium-sized or large set of countries with a BCA equal to or higher than the carbon price of the club, 52 out of 54 (96.3%) of tested scenarios end up with global coverage of the club. If we combine these two conditions with a high carbon price of the club (≥ 200 USD/tCO₂), 35 out of 36 (97.2%) tested scenarios result in full membership.

Different BCA revenue distribution methods were tested. First, the revenue from the region-specific BCA was distributed among club members – either equally or proportional to the shares of exports from non-members to members of the club. In these scenarios, if following a punitive strategy, full membership was achieved in all simulations (100%; 18 out of 18 tested scenarios). In scenarios with a symmetric strategy, 88.9% of the simulations (16 out of 18 tested scenarios) ended up with all regions joining the club. However, a lenient strategy only resulted in full membership in

22.2% of the simulations (4 out of 18), namely when the club is initiated by a medium-sized or large climate club under a low carbon price (50 USD/tCO₂).

Next, we examined the effects of returning a smaller or larger share of the revenue to non-members to help them cover abatement costs. This approach mitigates the risk of retaliation by returning a portion of the revenues to the countries that paid the BCA. Returning a smaller share, specifically less than half of the revenue, emerged as an effective approach to incentivise regions to join a climate club if initiated by a medium-sized (EU+) or large (EU+ and USA) group of countries. Notably, full membership was achieved in all the simulations under these conditions, even when adopting lenient strategies (18 out of 18; i.e. 100%). In the case of a small initial climate club, this approach is only effective when combined with a punitive strategy (3 out of 9 simulations; i.e. 33.3%). On the contrary, returning a larger share, exceeding half of the revenue, results in decreased motivation to join the club. This strategy is effective only if the club generates substantial revenues, as large compensation significantly reduces club benefits. Full membership under this BCA revenue distribution method was achieved in simulations initiated by a medium-sized or large region together with a high BCA level (11 out of 27 simulations; i.e. 40.7%).

As observed, a punitive strategy provides substantial benefits to club members while imposing considerable costs on non-members, resulting in convergence to a full agreement in most simulations. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that our model does not account for retaliation, while a punitive strategy may trigger such responses from regions outside the club. The risk of retaliation could, however, be mitigated if the initial climate club holds significant global influence (e.g., the European Union and the US). We find that this constellation most easily develops into a full agreement.

What do our findings mean in terms of concrete political action? The most realistic way forward is for the EU to invite the US to become a member of its emissions trading system. This would create a starting condition consistent with what we find to be a pathway with a high likelihood of culminating in a complete and ambitious climate agreement. Moreover, since the EU ETS already incorporates a gradual contraction of its cap, its carbon price will automatically increase over time, and its CBAM along with it. This means that all three initial conditions for a successful climate club will then be satisfied. Of course, the ideal approach would be that the EU ETS is extended to cover all emissions in the EU zone. The EU plan to implement ETS 2 for buildings and transport provides a good starting point.

References

- Ackerman, F., & Stanton, E. (2011). Climate risks and carbon prices: Revising the social cost of carbon. *Economics: The Open-Access, Open-Assessment E-Journal*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1973864>
- Anthoff, D., & Tol, R. (2011). The uncertainty about the social cost of carbon: A decomposition analysis using FUND. *Climatic Change*, 117. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-013-0706-7>
- Balint, T., Lamperti, F., Mandel, A., Napoletano, M., Roventini, A., & Sapio, A. (2017). Complexity and the economics of climate change: A survey and a look forward. *Ecological Economics*, 138, 252–265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.03.032>
- Bhagwati, J., & Mavroidis, P. C. (2007). Is action against US exports for failure to sign Kyoto Protocol WTO-legal? *World Trade Review*, 6(2), 299–310. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1474745607003291>
- Böhringer, C., Fischer, C., Rosendahl, K. E., & Rutherford, T. F. (2022). Potential impacts and challenges of border carbon adjustments. *Nature Climate Change*, 12, 22–29. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01250-z>
- Botzen, W., & van den Bergh, J. (2012). How sensitive is Nordhaus to Weitzman? Climate policy in DICE with an alternative damage function. *Economics Letters*, 117(1), 372–374. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2012.05.032>
- Bown, C. P., & Irwin, D. A. (2017). The GATT’s starting point: Tariff levels circa 1947. In M. Elsig, B. Hoekman, & J. Pauwelyn (Eds.), *Assessing the world trade organization: Fit for purpose?* (pp. 45–74). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108147644.004>
- Buchanan, J. M. (1965). An economic theory of clubs. *Economica*, 32(125), 1–14. Retrieved June 28, 2022, from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2552442>
- Carleton, T., & Greenstone, M. (2021). Updating the United States Government’s social cost of carbon. *University of Chicago, Becker Friedman Institute for Economics Working Paper No. 2021-04*, (4). <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3764255>
- Castro, J., Drews, S., Exadaktylos, F., Foramitti, J., Klein, F., Konc, T., Savin, I., & van den Bergh, J. (2020). A review of agent-based modeling of climate-energy policy. *WIREs Climate Change*, 11(4), e647. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.647>
- Climate Action Tracker. (2023). *Warming Projections Global Update. December 2023*. Retrieved December 12, 2023, from https://climateactiontracker.org/documents/1187/CAT_2023-12-05_GlobalUpdate_COP28.pdf
- Crippa, M., Guizzardi, D., Solazzo, E., Muntean, M., Schaaf, E., Monforti-Ferrario, F., Banja, M., Olivier, J., Grassi, G., Rossi, S., & Vignati, E. (2021). GHG emissions of all world countries. *2021 Report, EUR 30831 EN - JRC126363*. <https://doi.org/doi:10.2760/173513>
- Enerdata. (2023). *Marginal Abatement Cost Curves - MACC. Emissions reduction potentials and costs across sectors up to 2050*. Retrieved July 26, 2023, from <https://www.enerdata.net/research/marginal-abatement-cost-curves-MACCs-forecast.html>
- Falkner, R. (2016). The Paris Agreement and the new logic of international climate politics. *International Affairs*, 92(5), 1107–1125. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2346.12708>
- Falkner, R., Nasiritousi, N., & Reischl, G. (2021). Climate clubs: politically feasible and desirable? *Climate Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2021.1967717>
- Fawcett, A., Iyer, G., Clarke, L., Edmonds, J., Hultman, N., McJeon, H., Rogelj, J., Schuler, R., Alsalam, J., Asrar, G., Creason, J., Jeong, M., McFarland, J., Mundra, A., & Shi, W. (2015). Can Paris pledges avert severe climate change? *Science*, 350. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aad5761>
- Fischer, C., & Fox, A. K. (2012). Comparing policies to combat emissions leakage: Border carbon adjustments versus rebates. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 64(2), 199–216. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2012.01.005>
- Fowle, M. L. (2009). Incomplete environmental regulation, imperfect competition, and emissions leakage. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 1(2), 72–112. <https://doi.org/10.1257/pol.1.2.72>
- Gaulier, G., & Zignago, S. (2010). BACI: International trade database at the product-level. the 1994-2007 version. (2010-23). http://www.cepii.fr/CEPII/en/bdd_modele/bdd_modele.item.asp?id=37

- Gersbach, H., Hummel, N., & Winkler, R. (2021). Long-term climate treaties with a refunding club. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 80, 511–552. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-021-00597-3>
- Gsottbauer, E., & van den Bergh, J. (2013). Bounded rationality and social interaction in negotiating a climate agreement. *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics*, 13, 225–249. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-012-9182-1>
- Hepburn, C., & Beckerman, W. (2007). Ethics of the discount rate in the Stern Review on the Economics of Climate Change. *World Economics*, 8, 187–210.
- Hermwille, L., Lechtenböhrer, S., Åhman, M., Asselt, H., Bataille, C., Kronshage, S., Tönjes, A., Fishedick, M., Oberthür, S., Garg, A., Hall, C., Jochem, P., Schneider, C., Cui, R., Obergassel, W., Fragkos, P., Vishwanathan, S., & Trollip, H. (2022). A climate club to decarbonize the global steel industry. *Nature Climate Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01383-9>
- Hope, C. (2006). The social cost of carbon: What does it actually depend on? *Climate Policy*, 6(5), 565–572. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2006.9685621>
- Hovi, J., Sprinz, D. F., Sælen, H., & Underdal, A. (2017). The club approach: A gateway to effective climate co-operation? *British Journal of Political Science*, 49, 1071–1096. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007123416000788>
- Howard, P. H., & Sterner, T. (2017). Few and not so far between: A meta-analysis of climate damage estimates. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 68(1), 197–225.
- Interagency Working Group (IWG) on Social Cost of Greenhouse Gases. (2021). Technical support document: Social cost of carbon, methane, and nitrous oxide interim estimates under executive order 13990. *United States Government*. https://whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/TechnicalSupportDocument_SocialCostofCarbonMethaneNitrousOxide.pdf
- Iyer, G., Ou, Y., Edmonds, J., Fawcett, A. A., Hultman, N., McFarland, J., Fuhrman, J., Waldhoff, S., & McJeon, H. (2022). Ratcheting of climate pledges needed to limit peak global warming. *Nature Climate Change*, (12). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01508-0>
- Keohane, Petsonk, A., & Hanafi, A. (2015). Toward a club of carbon markets. *Climatic Change*, 144, 81–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-015-1506-z>
- Keohane & Victor, D. G. (2016). Cooperation and discord in global climate policy. *Nature Climate Change*, 6, 570–575. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2937>
- King, L. C., & van den Bergh, J. (2021). Potential carbon leakage under the Paris Agreement. *Climatic Change*, 165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-021-03082-4>
- Larch, M., & Wanner, J. (2017). Carbon tariffs: An analysis of the trade, welfare, and emission effects. *Journal of International Economics*, 109, 195–213. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2017.09.003>
- Lim, B., Hong, K., Yoon, J., Chang, J.-I., & Cheong, I. (2021). Pitfalls of the EU's carbon border adjustment mechanism. *Energies*, 14(21). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3390/en14217303>
- Martin, N., & van den Bergh, J. (2019). A multi-level climate club with national and sub-national members: Theory and application to US states. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab5045>
- Narayanan, B., Aguiar, A., & McDougall, R. (2012). Global Trade, Assistance, and Production: The GTAP 8 Data Base, Center for Global Trade Analysis. *Purdue University*. https://doi.org/http://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/databases/v8/v8_doco.asp
- Nordhaus, W. (1991). To slow or not to slow: The economics of the greenhouse effect. *The Economic Journal*, 101(407), 920–937. Retrieved July 20, 2022, from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2233864>
- Nordhaus, W. (2007). A Review of the Stern Review on the Economics of Climate Change. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 45(3), 686–702. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.45.3.686>
- Nordhaus, W. (2015). Climate clubs: Overcoming free-riding in international climate policy. *American Economic Review*, 105, 1339–1370. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.15000001>
- Nordhaus, W. (2019). Climate change: The ultimate challenge for economics. *American Economic Review*, 109, 1991–2014. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.109.6.1991>

- Nordhaus, W. (2021). Nordhaus 2021 - Why climate policy has failed: And how governments can do better. *Foreign Affairs*. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/world/2021-10-12/why-climate-policy-has-failed>
- Paroussos, L., Mandel, A., Fragkiadakis, K., Fragkos, P., Hinkel, J., & Vrontisi, Z. (2019). Climate clubs and the macro-economic benefits of international cooperation on climate policy. *Nature Climate Change*, 9, 542–546. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-019-0501-1>
- Pauwelyn, J., & Kleimann, D. (2020). *Trade related aspects of a carbon border adjustment mechanism – a legal assessment*. European Parliament; Directorate-General for External Policies of the Union (European Parliament). <https://doi.org/doi/10.2861/095035>
- Peters, G. P., Minx, J. C., Weber, C. L., & Edenhofer, O. (2011). Growth in emission transfers via international trade from 1990 to 2008. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 108(21), 8903–8908. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1006388108>
- Pindyck, R. S. (2019). The social cost of carbon revisited. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 94, 140–160. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2019.02.003>
- Rennert, K., Errickson, F., Prest, B. C., Rennels, L., Newell, W., Richard G. and Pizer, Kingdon, C., Wingenroth, J., Cooke, R., Parthum, B., Smith, D., Cromar, K., Diaz, D., Moore, F. C., Müller, U. K., Plevin, R. J., Raftery, A. E., Ševčíková, H., Sheets, H., Stock, J. H., ... Anthoff, D. (2022). Comprehensive evidence implies a higher social cost of CO₂. *Nature*, (4), 687–692. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05224-9>
- Rocchi, P., Serrano, M., Roca, J., & Arto, I. (2018). Border carbon adjustments based on avoided emissions: Addressing the challenge of its design. *Ecological Economics*, 145, 126–136. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.08.003>
- Sabel, C. F., & Victor, D. G. (2015). Governing global problems under uncertainty: Making bottom-up climate policy work. *Climatic Change*, 144, 15–27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-015-1507-y>
- Sapir, A. (2021). ‘The European Union’s carbon border mechanism and the WTO’, *Bruegel Blog*. Retrieved October 24, 2023, from <https://www.bruegel.org/blog-post/european-unions-carbon-border-mechanism-and-wto>
- Savin, I., Creutzig, F., Filatova, T., Foramitti, J., Konc, T., Niamir, L., Safarzynska, K., & van den Bergh, J. (2023). Agent-based modeling to integrate elements from different disciplines for ambitious climate policy. *WIREs Climate Change*, 14(2), e811. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.811>
- Shaia, F., & Colgan, J. D. (2021). *Presidential climate action on day one: A foreign-policy guide for the next U.S. President*. Retrieved November 30, 2021, from <https://watson.brown.edu/files/watson/imce/news/explore/2020/Final%5C%20CSL%5C%20Report.pdf>
- Shaw, D., & Fu, Y. H. (2020). Climate clubs with tax revenue recycling, tariffs, and transfers. *Climate Change Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2010007820400084>
- Smead, R., Sandler, R. L., Forber, P., & Basl, J. (2014). A bargaining game analysis of international climate negotiations. *Nature Climate Change*, 4, 442–445. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2229>
- Sprinz, D. F., Sælen, H., Underdal, A., & Hovi, J. (2018). The effectiveness of climate clubs under Donald Trump. *Climate Policy*, 18, 828–838. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2017.1410090>
- Stern, N. (2006). *The Economics of Climate Change: The Stern Review*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511817434>
- Tagliapietra, S. (2020). *2021 can be a climate breakthrough, but Biden and Europe need to talk*. Retrieved November 30, 2021, from <https://www.bruegel.org/2020/11/2021-can-be-a-climate-breakthrough-but-biden-and-europe-need-to-talk/>
- Tagliapietra, S., & Wolff, G. (2021a). Form a climate club: United States, European Union and China. *Nature (comment)*.
- Tagliapietra, S., & Wolff, G. B. (2021b). Conditions are ideal for a new climate club. *Energy Policy*, 158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112527>
- Tol, R., & Yohe, G. (2007). A Review of the Stern Review. *World Economics*, 7, 233–250.
- United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). (2023). *Emissions Gap Report 2023: Broken Record – Temperatures hit new highs, yet world fails to cut emissions*. Nairobi. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.59117/20.500.11822/43922>

- United States Bureau of Labor Statistics. (2023). *CPI Inflation Calculator*. Retrieved October 31, 2023, from https://www.bls.gov/data/inflation_calculator.htm
- United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). (2022). Report on the social cost of greenhouse gases: Estimates incorporating recent scientific advances. *National Center for Environmental Economics. Office of Policy. Climate Change Division. Office of Air and Radiation*. https://www.epa.gov/system/files/documents/2022-11/epa_scghg_report_draft_0.pdf
- van den Bergh, J., & Botzen, W. (2014). A lower bound to the social cost of CO₂ emissions. *Nature Climate Change*, *4*, 253–258. <https://doi.org/10.1038/NCLIMATE2135>
- van den Bergh, J. (2017). Rebound policy in the Paris Agreement: Instrument comparison and climate-club revenue offsets. *Climate Policy*, *17*(6), 801–813. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2016.1169499>
- van den Bergh, J., Angelsen, A., Baranzini, A., Botzen, W. J., Carattini, S., Drews, S., Dunlop, T., Galbraith, E., Gsottbauer, E., Howarth, R. B., Padilla, E., Roca, J., & Schmidt, R. C. (2020). A dual-track transition to global carbon pricing. *Climate Policy*, *20*, 1057–1069. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2020.1797618>
- Victor, D. G. (2011). *Global warming gridlock: Creating more effective strategies for protecting the planet*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511975714>
- Wang, P., Deng, X., Zhou, H., & Yu, S. (2019). Estimates of the social cost of carbon: A review based on meta-analysis. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, *209*, 1494–1507. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.11.058>
- Weischer, L., Morgan, J., & Patel, M. (2012). Climate Clubs: Can Small Groups of Countries make a Big Difference in Addressing Climate Change? *Review of European Community & International Environmental Law*. <http://csis.org/>
- Weitzman, M. L. (2009). On modeling and interpreting the economics of catastrophic climate change. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, *91*(1), 1–19.
- Weitzman, M. L. (2014). Fat tails and the social cost of carbon. *American Economic Review*, *104*(5), 544–46. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.104.5.544>
- World Bank. (2023). *The World Bank development indicators: "GDP (2021 US\$) - 2021"*. <https://data.worldbank.org/>
- World Trade Organization. (2023a). *Principles of the trading system. Understanding the WTO: basics*. Retrieved October 24, 2023, from https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/whatis_e/tif_e/fact2_e.htm
- World Trade Organization. (2023b). *WTO rules and environmental policies: GATT exceptions*. Retrieved October 25, 2023, from https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/envir_e/envt_rules_exceptions_e.htm

Appendix: Additional results

A1 BCA revenue remains within the club - Equal distribution

Small initial climate club: Switzerland as initial member

Figure A1: Climate-club dynamics with Switzerland as initial member, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for BCA revenue equally shared among club members. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

Medium initial climate club: EU+ as initial member

Figure A2: Climate-club dynamics with the EU+ as initial member, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for BCA revenue equally shared among club members. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

Large initial climate club: EU+ and the United States as initial members

Figure A3: Climate-club dynamics with the US and the EU+ as initial members, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for BCA revenue equally shared among club members. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

A2 BCA revenue remains within the club - Share of exports

Small initial climate club: Switzerland as initial member

Figure A4: Climate-club dynamics with Switzerland as initial member, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for BCA revenue shared proportionally to the share of exports from non-members to members of the club. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

Medium initial climate club: EU+ as initial member

Figure A5: Climate-club dynamics with the EU+ as initial member, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for BCA revenue shared proportionally to the share of exports from non-members to members of the club. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

Large initial climate club: EU+ and the United States as initial members

Figure A6: Climate-club dynamics with the US and the EU+ as initial members, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for BCA revenue shared proportionally to the share of exports from non-members to members of the club. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

A3 Part of the BCA covers abatement costs of potential members - $\alpha = 0.5$

Small initial climate club: Switzerland as initial member

Figure A7: Climate-club dynamics with Switzerland as initial member, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for part of BCA revenue returned to non-members to cover abatement costs - $\alpha = 1$. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

Medium initial climate club: EU+ as initial member

Figure A8: Climate-club dynamics with the EU+ as initial member, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for part of BCA revenue returned to non-members to cover abatement costs – $\alpha = 0.5$. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

Large initial climate club: EU+ and the United States as initial members

Figure A9: Climate-club dynamics with the US and the EU+ as initial members, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for part of BCA revenue returned to non-members to cover abatement costs – $\alpha = 0.5$. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

A4 Part of the BCA covers abatement costs of potential members - $\alpha = 1$

Small initial climate club: Switzerland as initial member

Figure A10: Climate-club dynamics with Switzerland as initial member, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for part of BCA revenue returned to non-members to cover abatement costs - $\alpha = 1$. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

Medium initial climate club: EU+ as initial member

Figure A11: Climate-club dynamics with the EU+ as initial member, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for part of BCA revenue returned to non-members to cover abatement costs $\alpha = 1$. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

Large initial climate club: EU+ and the United States as initial members

Figure A12: Climate-club dynamics with the US and the EU+ as initial members, for varying carbon prices and region-specific BCAs, and for part of BCA revenue returned to non-members to cover abatement costs – $\alpha = 1$. The BCAs are set at 50% below (green, lenient strategy), equal to (blue, symmetric strategy), and 50% above (purple, punitive strategy) the carbon prices of 50, 200, and 400 USD/tCO₂.

A5 Uniform BCA

Figure A13: Climate-club dynamics with Switzerland, the EU+, and the US and the EU+ as initial members, for carbon prices and uniform BCAs of 50 USD/tCO₂ (light blue), 200 USD/tCO₂ (blue), and 400 USD/tCO₂ (dark blue). BCA revenue remains within the club, distributed according to the share of exports.